

UZBEK TERMINOLOGY AND SPEECH ISSUES AT THE STAGE OF ITS DEVELOPMENT

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It is known that a lot of research has been conducted in linguistics to clarify various aspects of field terms. Linguists N. Dmitriev, N. Baskakov, A. Reformatsky, V. Danilenko, N. Mamatov, S. Ibrohimov, M. Abdiev and others contributed to the research of these problems.

The study of its terminological system based on the materials of Turkic languages began in the 50s of the last century. By this time, terms for various fields were created in a number of Turkish languages, textbooks were published, the translation of scientific and technical literature and various training manuals from Russian had a positive effect on the formation of the terminology of the fields and contained large linguistic materials that had been formed until the 1950s. Studying the terms of aggregated networks, their regulation set a number of tasks for the science of linguistics. In this way, the first scientific works investigating the issues of terminology in the national Turkic languages came to the fore.

The first work on the terminology of Uzbek language networks is the work of N. Mamatov entitled "Terminology of Uzbek cotton", which was defended in 1955. The development of terms related to cotton farming in the work, their classification, the different aspects of terms from words and phrases, the definition of the term, the history of the development of cotton farming in Uzbekistan and the emergence of new terms in connection with it, the decisive position of internal and external sources in the enrichment of the terminology of Uzbek cotton farming are detailed analysis. done

In Uzbek linguistics, new steps have been taken in the study of terms, that is, researches on scientific terminology, professions, lexicon of the Uzbek language,

as well as encyclopedias and explanatory dictionaries have been launched. In October 1989, the Uzbek language became a state language. Also, it is appropriate to mention another important event. On August 31, 1991, the Republic of Uzbekistan was one of the first republics of the former union to declare its independence. These important facts cross the important task of developing the process of exchange of linguistic information, which has been established in the language for a long time, on a larger scale. In conclusion, he emphasized the need to revise the emerging linguistic materials in the fields covering all aspects of life within the framework of the laws and requirements of the Uzbek language. In particular, issues of perfect creation of socio-political documents and literature play an important role in this process. After all, in Article 7 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the State Language, "The current scientific rules and norms of the Uzbek literary language shall be observed in the spheres where the state language is officially valid."

It can be said that the terms of today's Uzbek linguistics can fully express the concepts related to linguistic phenomena. It can be said that a dictionary of terms representing concepts used at all language levels has been created. These include synonyms, antonyms, homonyms, paronyms, phrases, idioms, etymological dictionary, spelling dictionary, dictionary of direct linguistic terms.

Uzbek linguistic terms also have a long history. In Mahmud Koshgari's work "Devonu lugotit turk" you can find a lot of terms related to linguistics. Also, in the work of Alisher Navoi, who studied the language as a special object of research, "Muhokamatul lug'atayn" you can find terms that express the concepts of philology of that time. It is known that at the beginning of the last century, the representatives of movements such as Pan-Islamists and Pan-Turkists reacted to different field terms and caused the origin of diversity in the language. Supporters of the Pan-Islamic group were in favor of using Arabic terms instead of Russian terms in our lexicon. Supporters of the Pan-Turkist trend were completely against the introduction of international words and terms into the Uzbek language. They

suggested using only words from their own language to express new concepts in the language. They suggested using obsolete words, borrowing words from other Turkic languages when they are not possible, and using Arabic and Persian terms when that is also not possible. These circumstances did not make it possible to properly convey the issues of terms and terminology to the people. As a result, it is known from the literature that at the beginning of the 20th century there were differences and confusions in linguistic terms.

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